

Integration of flux and remote sensing data and modelling approaches to quantify water and carbon fluxes from regional to continental scale (2013)

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Project Objectives

Terrestrial ecosystems annually sequester about one quarter of the anthropogenic CO₂ emissions (Canadell & Raupach 2008). It is of great importance to understand the drivers of carbon uptake and release on timescales ranging from sub-diurnal to multi-annual. We explore the improvement in Land Surface Models (LSMs) that can be achieved through integration with remote sensing and flux tower observations by (i) using remote sensing data to quantify model parameters in space and time, and (ii) using footprint weighted remote sensing data and model output to benchmark the model with flux measurements and to explore the interannual variability in the carbon dynamics in continental Australia by analyzing 30 years of model output using the CSIRO Atmosphere Biosphere Land Exchange model (CABLE) and a much simpler model, based on light use efficiency, to analyse trends, covariance with climate drivers and indices (e.g. ENSO, IOD, Monsoon) and spatially attribute these anomalies to the underlying processes.

Leaf Area Index (LAI) and the Fraction of Photosynthetically Active Radiation absorbed by vegetation (fPAR or FAPAR) are key biophysical variables controlling the exchanges of energy, carbon and water between the Earth surface and atmosphere (Ganguly *et al.*, 2008). These variables can be generated from various satellite sensors at different spatial and temporal resolution. This leads to several issues in remote sensing science, including scaling and sensor related topics (e.g. choice of radiative transfer model, mixing of soil and vegetation types and spectral characteristics, spatial resolution, calibration, measurement geometry etc.).

The group aimed to:

- Explore the improvement in Land Surface Models (LSMs) that can be achieved through integration with remote sensing and flux tower observations by: (i) using remote sensing data to quantify variables used in LSMs in space and time; and (ii) using footprint weighted remote sensing data and model output to benchmark the model with flux measurements.
- Explore the interannual variability in the carbon dynamics of continental Australia by analysing 30 years of model output using a research version of the CSIRO Atmosphere Biosphere Land Exchange model (CABLE) in the BIOS2 framework (see Notes) and a much simpler model, based on light use efficiency, to analyse trends, covariance with climate drivers and indices (e.g. ENSO, IOD, Monsoon) and spatially attribute these anomalies to the underlying processes.
- Assess the uncertainty that arises from using various LAI/fPAR products when computing carbon and water fluxes.

Future work will compare the satellite products with fractional cover datasets from TERN and SLATS (the Statewide Landcover and Trees Study of the Queensland government) transects.

Methods

CABLE/BIOS2 (Haverd *et al.*, 2012) were run with local meteorology for LAI/fPAR values derived from various sensors and hence pixel sizes to: (i) assess which product leads to the best agreement between weighted model output and flux tower observation; and (ii) assess the uncertainty associated with using the AVHRR LAI/fPAR (which is available for 30+ years). For model validation we agreed to use data from two towers with >10 years of time series (Tumbarumba and Howard Springs) and data of 14 towers with 1-4 years time series, which provides good spatial and temporal coverage. The degradation of the modelling results using gridded meteorological drivers rather than local meteorological data in conjunction with the AVHRR data will be assessed elsewhere.

A covariance analysis was conducted between climate indices, climate drivers and the time series of remote sensing and measured fluxes. We assess the temporal scale at which we observe highest linearization between the major drivers and the fluxes by determining where the change in the covariance matrix reaches a minimum. This is the temporal scale at which simpler models are expected to perform best. Two simple models are used for testing with MODIS and AVHRR data: BESS, a coupled-process model which estimates gross primary productivity and evapotranspiration (Ryu *et al.*, 2011); and a simple model, the Ecosystem Production in Space and Time (EPISaT) model which is based on light use efficiency and is still under development.

After establishing the model uncertainties, we ran the models for the last 30 years and collected further GPP and ET products (NASA-AMES, Max Plank Institute, etc.). We analysed trends, covariance with climate drivers and indices (e.g. ENSO, IOD, Monsoon) and spatially attributed these anomalies to the underlying processes. Having multiple model products allows for an 'ensemble-view' for quantifying the effects of climate models on the fluxes.

The sites used and data availability is shown in Table 1. Where gap filling is necessary, a standardized approach was applied (Reichstein *et al.*, 2005).

Methods (continued)

Site	Coordinates	Time Period
Howard Springs	12.4952 S 131.1501 E	01/2001-12/2011
Adelaide River	13.0769 S 131.1178 E	01/2007-05/2009
Daly River Savanna	14.1592 S 131.3833 E	01/2007-12/2011
Daly R Pasture	14.1592 S 131.3833 E	01/2007-12/2011
Dry Creek	15.2588 S 132.3706 E	01/2010-06/2011
Sturt Plains	17.1507 S 133.3502 E	01/2008-12/2010
Alice Springs	22.283 S 133.249 E	09/2010-12/2011
Calperum	34.0027 S 140.5877 E	08/2010-12/2011
Wombat State Forest	37.4222 S 144.0944 E	02/2010-08/2011
Wallaby Creek	37.4262 S 145.1872 E	01/2005-12/2008
Tumbarumba	35.6566 S 148.1517 E	02/2001-12/2011

Table 1: Location of OzFlux sites and time periods used for model evaluation and parameter estimation.

NOTES

Land surface models: CABLE/BIOS2 have been successfully used to simulate Australia's terrestrial carbon and water cycle for the period 1990-2011, with monthly outputs at 0.05° (~5km) spatial resolution (Harverd *et al.*, 2012).

BESS was used to compute global terrestrial estimates of gross primary productivity and evapotranspiration between 2001 and 2003 at 1-5 km resolution.

Simple ecosystem productivity model: The EPISaT model, currently under development, builds on the well founded and tested light use efficiency approach and incorporates recent developments in our understanding of the relationships between Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Vapour Pressure Deficit (VPD), Soil Moisture (SM) and Photosynthesis. In early 2013, for comparison against the CABLE/BIOS2 1990-2011 model runs, EPISaT will be run at 0.05° (~5km) spatial resolution over the same period.

Footprint model: Flux footprint functions estimate location and relative importance of e.g. carbon and water vapour sources influencing flux measurements. Reliable footprint calculations from e.g. Lagrangian stochastic models are computationally expensive and cannot readily be computed for long-term observational programs. More easily accessible footprint estimates are provided through a scaling procedure for flux footprint functions (Kljun *et al.*, 2004). This algorithm was adjusted to account for along and crosswind contributions in the source area. Footprint estimates were calculated for the full periods for the sites listed in Table 1.

Major Findings

The fPAR values derived from several satellite products for Howard Springs (Figure 1) showed that: (a) different satellite products show different seasonality, (b) different satellite products have different gains, i.e. will not show the same increase of fPAR through the seasons, and (c) different satellite products have different offsets (not shown here), which can largely be explained by scaling issues.

Figure 1: Seasonality of recurrent vegetation in Howard Springs as seen by several remote sensors. Note that the minimum seasonal fPAR value for each product is fixed at 0.01 to make it easier to compare seasonal magnitudes and timing of the maximum and minimum fPAR estimates.

Data analysis for the Tumbarumba flux site showed that coherences between fluxes and drivers are generally strongest on annual time periods. Coherence is strongest between incoming shortwave radiation and fluxes and is generally stronger between temperature and fluxes than for vapor pressure deficit, soil water content or precipitation on fluxes. On multi-annual time scales, a good coherence between the MEI (multivariate ENSO index) and carbon and water fluxes could be established.

The footprint parameterisation of flux footprint functions (Kljun *et al.*, 2004) for stable stratification was improved. Using tower turbulence observations and airborne LiDAR scans at the Tumbarumba site, key model parameters were derived specific to the site and footprint climatology was calculated for a 3-month period. This allows better determination of the source/sink area that influences the measured fluxes and therefore better comparison with model output.

CABLE/BIOS2 was successfully used to simulate Australia's terrestrial carbon and water cycle. It could be shown that simultaneous constraint by multiple data types is useful since this mitigates bias from any single observation type, but that eddy flux measurements provide a significantly tighter constraint on continental net primary production than the other data types. The model outputs were tested against independent observations and estimates / uncertainties of terms in the long-term mean Australian carbon and water budgets analysed. The important questions addressed were: (i) what fraction of evapotranspiration bypasses plants on the Australian continent? (ii) how big is net primary productivity of grasses compared to woody vegetation? and (iii) how does the average inter-annual variability of Australia's net ecosystem productivity compare to Australia's total anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions? (Harverd *et al.*, 2012)

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science and management?

Through this work we are able to establish:

- the uncertainties associated with using non-local meteorological input data and relatively low resolution fPAR/LAI input to compute Australian water and carbon fluxes
- the temporal scales for which simpler models can be used

This project generates a time series of fluxes and drivers that is long enough (30 years) to investigate the impact of climate models with low periodicities such as ENSO, IOD and Monsoon. Anomalies were spatially attributed to the underlying processes.

Not only will we now be able to address questions around the quantification of water and carbon uptake, and the natural variation from year to year, but this is one of the first attempts to look at low frequency climate models and their impact on the carbon and water cycle.

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